

Valide Sultan Mosque in Rethymno

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The Valide Sultan Mosque in Rethymno was established after the Ottoman Conquest of Rethymno in 1646. The mosque is likely a converted Venetian church, as can be seen from its rectangular structure, which is typical of Venetian churches on Crete. The two domes and single minaret of the structure were added after its conversion into a mosque. As of 2023, it is not possible to visit the mosque, although the minaret can be seen over the skyline of Rethymno. The title 'Valide Sultan' refers to the mother of the Sultan (Kösem Sultan, the mother of Sultan Ibrahim). At the time of its construction, the Valide Sultan Mosque featured prominently just inside the main gate to the Old Town of Rethymno. According to Evliya Celebi, an Ottoman traveller who visited Crete ca. 1668, the Valide Sultan Mosque was associated with the Valide Mosque Imaret (soup kitchen) as well as a dervish lodge (Book 8, vol. 1, pp. 379-381.)

Date Range: 1650 CE - 1923 CE

Region: Valide Sultan Mosque in Rethymno

Region tags: Greece

The Valide Sultan Mosque in Rethymno.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Zilli, Mehmed (Evliya). *Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*. Translated by Seyit Kahraman. Vol. 8/1. İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010.
- Source 2: Zilli, Mehmed (Evliya). *Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*. Edited by Seyit Ali Kahraman, Yücel Dağlı, and Robert Dankoff. Vol. VIII. İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2003.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://historicalcrete.ims.forth.gr/Toponyms/listing/valinte-tzami>
- Source 1 Description: Interactive atlas of historical place names in Crete by Kostas Papadakis

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The mosque is located inside the main gate to the city.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape
– Rectangular

↳ One single feature
– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ A group of structures:
– No

↳ A group of features:
– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– Yes

Notes: Originally, an imaret (soup kitchen) and dervish lodge were associated with the mosque, although these no longer remain (or possibly have been repurposed into other structures).

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:
– Individual

– Worship

↳ Worship:
– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– Yes

Notes: Structure is partially destroyed (portico no longer remains).

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
– For political reasons

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: God (monotheistic)

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Associated with Ottoman conquest of Crete

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– War/battle

Notes: The mosque is associated with the Ottoman conquest of Crete, but was not solely built to commemorate this conquest.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: In the seventeenth century, a soup kitchen (imaret) and dervish lodge were associated with the mosque.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque is the predominant structure.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Carved inscriptions appear above the doorway.

↳ On the inside:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The calligraphic inscriptions above the entrance are carved in relief

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: A supreme high god is worshipped, but is not considered to be physically present.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: all-powerful

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels and djinn may be considered to be present at this place.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: 50-200

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Daily/Weekly

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: Congregational Friday prayer was required for men, but optional for women.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– No

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: N/A.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

- No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

- Yes

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Priests
 - No

- ↳ Local elites
 - Yes

- ↳ Private contributions
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: N/A.

- ↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

- Yes [specify]: Imaret (soup kitchen)

Notes: The imaret (soup kitchen) served rich and poor alike; it is possible that Eid feasts occurred here.

Are festivals present:

- Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: twice annually

Notes: The main holidays were Eid ul Adha and Eid ul Fitr

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Non-Muslim members of society may not have participated in the festivals.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 50-200

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: It is likely that the sheikh associated with the mosque had living quarters originally; however, these quarters are no longer extant.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The mosque was likely supported by a vakf (charitable endowment).

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: It is likely that the vakf endowment included lands.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: There was an imaret (soup kitchen).

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but not exclusively.

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Scripture (Quran) likely features in interior calligraphic carvings

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Valide Sultan Mosque in Rethymno, Zilli, Mehmed (Evliya). *Evliya çelebi seyahatnamesi*. Translated by Seyit Kahraman. Vol. 8/1. İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010.

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